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Exploring Innovative Methods for Air Dust Pollution Monitoring using Satellite Data and Products: a Comparative Study of Chalidiki (Greece) and Ihalainen (Finland)

Diploma Thesis

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DIPLOMA THESIS ASSIGNMENT

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Thesis title

Nové možnosti monitoringu polévatvého prachu s využitím volně dostupných satelitních dat a produktů: srovnávací studie pro Chalkidki (Řecko) a Ihalainen (Finsko)

Objectives of thesis

Cílem práce je testovat a validovat nové možnosti monitoringu prachového znečištění s využitím volně dostupných satelitních dat a produktů poskytovaných zdarma v rámci programů ESA a NASA. Jednotlivé datové vstupy budou validovány s využitím volně dostupných dat pořizovaných lokálními monitorovacími stanicemi. Pro dvě různé oblasti (Řecko a Finsko) budou vytvořeny predikční statistické modely a modely časových řad a trendů.

Methodology

Testovací lokality: oblasti zatížené povrchovou těžbou ve východní části Řeckého poloostrova Chalkidi a ve Finském vnitrozemí (okolí města Lappeenranta)

Nové postupy vytvořené v rámci této diplomové práce se zaměří na automatizaci procesů umožňující ve výsledku přímé vyhodnocení a validaci satelitních dat a produktů (CAM5 PM10, MODIS AOD ...). Dílčí kroky jsou definovány takto:

- Automatizované zpracování satelitních dat pořizovaných s vysokou časovou frekvencí, jejich agregace do produktů, které odpovídají časovému oknu validačních dat pořizovaných pozemními monitorovacími stanicemi
- Vytvoření kvantitativních modelů a jejich validace pomocí dat monitorovacích stanic
- Aplikace modelů do delších časových řad, modelování časových řad novými nekonvenčními způsoby (e.g. metody strojového učení)

The proposed extent of the thesis

50 stran

Keywords

DPZ, Copernicus, PM10, polétavý prach, těžební oblasti, environmentální monitoring, analýzy časových řad

Recommended information sources

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Author's statement

I hereby declare that I have independently elaborated the diploma thesis with the topic of: *Exploring Innovative Methods for Air Dust Pollution Monitoring using Satellite Data and Products: a Comparative Study of Chalidiki (Greece) and Ihalainen (Finland)* and that I have cited all the information sources that I used in the thesis and that are also listed at the end of the thesis in the list of used information sources.

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In Prague on March 31, 2025

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Petra Sedláčková

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Abstract

Surface mining can have a significant impact on various aspects of the environment, including human health. One of the most harmful effects on the human body has the particulate pollution that can be released into the air during mining operations. Particles smaller than 10 micrometres, known as PM10, can be inhaled and linked to respiratory and cardiovascular diseases. Monitoring this type of pollution is challenging because of its spatial distribution. The atmosphere is a three-dimensional space, and it is impossible to cover an entire area with in-situ monitoring stations. However, remote sensing satellite data provides an effective alternative for monitoring airborne dust. Although satellite-based data have limitations, they provide stable spatial and temporal coverage that is valuable for long-term monitoring and offers advantages for monitoring large, inaccessible areas.

This study was carried out at two sites, on the Chalkidiki peninsula in Greece and in the Finnish inland near the city of Lappeenranta, between years 2015-2024 and 2013-2024, respectively. To achieve the objectives of this work, local in-situ measurements of PM10 pollution provided by the Finnish Meteorological Institute and the Hellas-Gold environmental platform and two remote sensing data products were used: the CAMS European air quality re/analysis dataset provided by the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) and the Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) data at 0.55 micrometres from NASA's MODIS Terra and Aqua satellites at 10, 3 and 1 km resolution.

All data were aggregated to daily values for further evaluation, from which CAMS data showed strong correlations with in-situ data, making it a valuable resource for monitoring, with correlation coefficients (r_s) around 0.8, depending on the site. In contrast, MODIS data presented a different scenario, with correlations peaking at 0.5 and in some cases becoming negative. This incompatibility may be due to long periods of missing data because of cloud cover. CAMS data were also aggregated into monthly and annual values to observe trends and seasonality. These showed a decreasing trend in concentrations, suggesting an improvement in air quality over the years at both locations. Machine learning techniques were also used, including Prophet and BSTS for trend and seasonality prediction, and XGBoost and Random Forest for short-term prediction. Prophet and XGBoost were found to be more accurate with this type of data.

Future steps in this research will include further data modelling and prediction methods, with a focus on integrating other machine learning methods, and exploring additional remote sensing datasets suitable for developing an optimal workflow for this use case.

Key words: Remote sensing, Copernicus, PM10, dust pollution, mining areas, environmental monitoring, time series analysis

Abstrakt

Povrchová těžba může mít významný dopad na různé aspekty životního prostředí, včetně lidského zdraví. Polévatý prach, který se může uvolňovat do ovzduší během těžebních prací, má negativní vliv na lidský organismus. Částice menší než 10 mikrometrů, známé jako PM10, mohou být vdechovány a jsou spojovány s respiračními a kardiovaskulárními chorobami. Monitorování tohoto typu znečištění je náročné kvůli jeho prostorovému rozložení. Atmosféra je trojrozměrný prostor a není možné pokrýt celou oblast monitorovacími stanicemi in-situ. Družicová data dálkového průzkumu Země však mohou být účinnou alternativou pro monitorování polévatého prachu. Přestože satelitní data mají svá omezení, poskytují stabilní prostorové a časové pokrytí, které je cenné pro dlouhodobé monitorování a nabízí výhody pro monitorování rozsáhlých, nepřístupných oblastí.

Tato studie byla provedena na dvou místech, na poloostrově Chalkidiki v Řecku a ve finském vnitrozemí poblíž města Lappeenranta, mezi lety 2015-2024 (respektive 2013-2024). K dosažení cílů této práce byla použita místní in-situ měření znečištění PM10, poskytovaná Finským meteorologickým ústavem a environmentální platformou Hellas-Gold. Dále dva datové produkty dálkového průzkumu Země: soubor dat CAMS pro re/analýzu kvality evropského ovzduší poskytovaný službou Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) a data optické aerosolové hloubky (AOD) na úrovni 0,55 mikrometru z družic MODIS Terra a Aqua společnosti NASA s rozlišením 10, 3 a 1 km.

Všechna data byla agregována do denních hodnot pro další vyhodnocení. Data CAMS vykazují silnou korelaci s daty in-situ, což z nich činí cenný zdroj pro monitorování, s korelačními koeficienty (r_s) kolem 0,8 v závislosti na lokalitě. Naproti tomu data MODIS vykazují odlišné výsledky, přičemž korelace dosahují maximálně hodnoty 0,5 a v některých případech jsou záporné. Tato nekompatibilita může být způsobena dlouhými obdobími chybějících dat v důsledku oblačnosti. Data CAMS byla také agregována do měsíčních a ročních hodnot, aby bylo možné sledovat dlouhodobé trendy a sezónnost. Ty ukázaly klesající trend koncentrací, což naznačuje zlepšení kvality ovzduší v průběhu let v obou lokalitách. Byly také použity techniky strojového učení, včetně Prophet a BSTS pro předpověď trendů a sezónnosti a XGBoost a Random Forest pro krátkodobou předpověď. Ukázalo se, že Prophet a XGBoost jsou s tímto typem dat kompatibilnější.

Budoucí kroky v tomto výzkumu budou zahrnovat další metody modelování a predikcí těchto dat, se zaměřením na integraci dalších metod strojového učení a zkoumání dalších datových DPZ zdrojů vhodných pro vývoj optimálního pracovního postupu pro použití v této problematice.

Klíčová slova: DPZ, Copernicus, PM10, polévatý prach, těžební oblasti, environmentální monitoring, analýzy časových řad

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	8
2	Objectives of the thesis	8
3	Literary research.....	9
3.1	Air Pollution - overview.....	9
3.2	Particular air pollution.....	11
3.2.1	Classification of PM.....	11
3.2.2	Sources of PM	11
3.2.3	Mine dust pollution	12
3.2.4	Impact of PM pollution	12
3.3	PM monitoring	13
3.3.1	In-situ monitoring	13
3.3.2	Remote sensing techniques	14
3.3.3	Modelling and forecasting of dust pollution	16
3.4	Limits, legislative and standards	17
4	Characteristics of the study area	19
4.1	Greece	19
4.2	Finland	20
5	Data and Methodology	21
5.1	Datasets	21
5.1.1	In-situ data.....	21
5.1.2	Remote sensing data and products	23
5.2	Data processing	24
5.2.1	Data acquisition and preprocessing.....	24
5.2.2	Statistical analysis	25
5.2.3	Spatial data analysis	27
6	Results.....	29
6.1	Descriptive statistics of in-situ data	29
6.2	Stations specificity analysis	32
6.2.1	Principal components analysis of stations data.....	32
6.2.2	Visualisation of annual and monthly averages.....	33
6.3	Correlations of CAMS and MODIS data with in-situ datasets.....	38

6.4	Trends and seasonality	40
6.5	Spatio-temporal analysis	44
6.5.1	Long-term spatio-temporal analysis.....	44
6.5.2	Annual spatio-temporal analysis	47
6.6	PM10 Time series modelling and forecasting.....	50
7	Discussion	54
8	Conclusion	56
9	Bibliography and sources	57

1 Introduction

Air dust pollution has been a part of life on Earth since the beginning. In the early days, it was natural disasters, such as volcanic eruptions or forest fires, that released large amounts of particles into the air. Nowadays, pollution from natural sources has decreased, but that doesn't mean the air is cleaner. What has increased are particles from combustion engines or dust from other industrial activities such as mining (Tiwary and Williams, 2019). Recent studies have shown that this type of pollution affects human health, vegetation, the socio-economics and other aspects of life on our planet (Gautam and B. Bolia, 2020).

For this reason, it is important to know exactly how polluted a given locality is. Most local monitoring is done using in-situ measurements, which have limitations in covering large areas. In this case, satellite data products are a useful complement and can provide satisfactory results with good spatial and temporal resolution. These data can help to assess appropriate measures to reduce the effects of air pollution and to find the solution for cleaner air and healthier lives.

2 Objectives of the thesis

The work will focus on the overall assessment of dust pollution at two selected sites affected by surface mining activities in the eastern part of the Chalkidiki peninsula in Greece and in the inland area of Finland, Ihalainen near the city of Lappeenranta. The data used for this analysis are local in-situ measurements and in addition the possibility of using remote sensing data products (CAMS PM10 and MODIS AOD) for dust pollution monitoring will be tested.

Specific steps include automated processing of satellite data products and their aggregation to match the spatial and temporal resolution and make all the products compatible. Statistics will be calculated for evaluation, quantitative models will be developed and applied to longer time series, and predictions will be made using statistical models and machine learning techniques.

3 Literary research

3.1 Air Pollution - overview

The air we breathe is one of the things that makes our planet habitable. Consisting mainly of nitrogen, oxygen, argon, water and a large number of trace gases, the chemistry of the atmosphere is a complicated subject in itself (Gaffney and Marley, 2003). But the atmosphere is a three-dimensional space where all interactions affect each other and where anthropogenic, natural and atmospheric processes work together to form a the whole in which we live. It is not uncommon for these substances to exceed limits and be found in high concentrations, even though they shouldn't be in the atmosphere at all.

There can be a long list of definitions of what air pollution is and what it is not. According to Tiwary and Williams (2019), air pollution is “the presence of substances in the atmosphere that can cause adverse effects to man and the environment”. It describes the unwanted contamination of chemicals or materials that leads to a reduction in overall air quality. These pollutants can be either in solid, liquid or gaseous form, from stationary or areal sources with various temporal duration (Tiwary and Williams, 2019).

This contamination can come from both natural and anthropogenic sources (Tiwary and Williams, 2019). Natural (or biogenic) sources include disasters such as forest fires caused by lightning or drought, large volcanic eruptions or sand storms, occurring in high arid areas. These events have always occurred naturally on our planet and are more or less time limited (Gaffney and Marley, 2003). Anthropogenic (or human-made) sources, on the other hand, are relatively new in the Earth's history. The greatest expansion is dated to the beginning of Industrial Revolution, when humans began to use fossil fuels. Pollution from motor vehicles, which still make up the majority of public transport today, mining, construction activities or even agricultural land use and landfill decomposition are events that release pollution on a long-term basis (Bai *et al.*, 2018).

Another way of classifying pollutants is to divide them into primary and secondary pollutants. Primary pollutants are those that are emitted directly into the atmosphere. These are typically particular pollutants, carbon monoxide, nitrogen oxides or a variety of other emissions. Secondary pollutants are formed later in the atmosphere from primary pollutants after a chemical reaction in the presence of oxygen (e.g. photolysis of nitrogen dioxide to form ozone, etc.) (Gaffney and Marley, 2003; Gautam and B. Bolia, 2020).

Either anthropogenic or natural, primary or secondary pollutants, high or low in concentration, every air pollutant has an impact on life on Earth. The effects on human health are primarily associated with respiratory or cardiovascular diseases

(Tiwary and Williams, 2019). Depending on the duration of exposure to pollution, both acute and chronic effects can be observed, associated with symptoms such as throat, eye and nose irritation, coughing, nausea and headaches, or pneumonia. Long-term exposure increases the risk of asthma, heart disease and even cancer. Young children or, on the other side, old and otherwise ill individuals are more often affected and susceptible to mentioned diseases (Gautam and B. Bolia, 2020). Similar problems can also affect animals, whether wild or domesticated.

The plant part of the environment is also affected by air pollution. They can be directly affected by dust cover on leaves, which leads to lack of light necessary for photosynthesis and weakening of the whole plant (Tiwary and Williams, 2019). Another effect is caused by high concentrations of sulphur dioxide or nitrogen oxides, which react with oxygen and water in the upper atmosphere and form acid rain. This precipitation has a low pH which seeps into the soil, depriving it of essential nutrients and releasing aluminium. This makes it difficult for trees to absorb water from the soil and even their needles or leaves are harmed. Prolonged exposure to acid rain leads to the destruction of entire local ecosystems (Gaffney and Marley, 2003).

On a global scale, air pollution affects all life on our planet with gases known as greenhouse gases (Amato and Akdis, 2020). Water vapour, carbon dioxide, methane or, for example ozone, accumulate in the higher layers of the atmosphere, where they form a barrier that blocks reflected radiation from the surface from returning to space. By remaining in the atmosphere, this radiation causes the planet to heat up. Without the greenhouse effect, our planet would be much cooler and probably uninhabitable, but extreme concentrations of these gases cause the temperature to rise faster than is natural. This now frequently mentioned problem is referred as global warming (Gaffney and Marley, 2003; Tiwary and Williams, 2019).

As already mentioned, air pollution has impact on every living part of the Earth. The connection between climate change, environmental degradation, socio-economic impacts or food production makes air pollution a complex issue with multiple variables (Gautam and B. Bolia, 2020).

For the purposes of this work, the following chapters will focus on solid, particular pollutants emitted mainly by the mining industrial activities.

3.2 Particular air pollution

Particular air pollution, airborne dust pollution, particulate matter (PM) or even solid aerosol are the terms used for the category of particles suspended in the air. These particles vary in the size, shape or chemical composition (Gokul *et al.*, 2023). Their common characteristics is that they are small enough to be suspended in the air and carried over long distances by the wind. Particles of this size are almost unaffected by gravity, and their low settling speeds helps them to remain in the air for even a few days, until they are washed out by rain or trapped by vegetation.(Tiwary and Williams, 2019).

3.2.1 Classification of PM

All particles in the air are collectively known as suspended particulate matter (SPM) or total suspended particulate (TSP) (Tiwary and Williams, 2019). Based on the size of the particles, pollutants are often divided into three groups: PM 10, PM 2.5 and PM 0.1. Particles with a diameter of less than 10 μm are known as coarse particulate matter and are called PM10. PM 2.5 are particles smaller than 2.5 μm , known as fine particulate matter. The smallest particles, smaller than 0.1 μm , are called ultrafine particles or PM 0.1 (Gokul *et al.*, 2023). Other terms often used to describe PM pollutants include aerosols, which refer to any solid or liquid particle from submicron to several microns in size, or dust, which refer to solid particles larger than 1 μm that remain suspended in the air (Tiwary and Williams, 2019).

3.2.2 Sources of PM

As discussed earlier, dust pollution can be dispersed into the air by natural processes or by anthropogenic activities. Natural sources are often large temporal events that affect the environment on a larger spatial scale. Typical examples include dust storms or the dispersion of volcanic particles from eruptions, etc. (Feuerstein and Schepanski, 2018). Although these large events are perceived negatively because of their impact on human life, it is important to remember that the atmospheric dust cycle is a fundamental component of the global climate system, affecting the Earth's albedo, the formation of precipitation nuclei and the transport of nutrients over long distances. (Abdelkader *et al.*, 2015; Xia *et al.*, 2022).

Air pollution from industrial activities and processes often has a different dynamic, as these pollutants are mostly continuously dispersed. Although particles can travel long distances, the spatial extent of pollution from individual sources tends to be local. These sources include all types of manufacturing industries, vehicle emissions, etc. For this type of pollution, it is not only the size of the particles that is problematic, but also their chemical composition (Gokul *et al.*, 2023). For anthropogenic sources, smaller particles (below 2.5 μm) are more likely to be combustion products, while larger particles below 10 μm usually include mechanically generated dust (Lippmann, 2012).

3.2.3 Mine dust pollution

Mining activities, as an anthropogenic source of PM pollution, contribute significantly to the degradation and damage of the surrounding environment. In particular, open-pit mining operations are the main source of dust pollution, affecting both the workplace and the general public (Yu and Zahidi, 2023). These operations, contributing to higher concentration of particles suspended in the air, include the perforation and blasting of rocks, additional treatment of the extracted minerals (sorting and screening or machining into desired shapes), followed by the transport and dumping of the remaining material on spoil heaps (Monjezi *et al.*, 2009; Du, Wang and Wang, 2022).

Particles generated by mining processes are mainly deposited near the mine site. These typically vary in sizes and their chemical composition depend on the geological substrate and the material of the extracted mineral itself. Depending on their size, the smaller the particles are, the longer they can remain in the air, and their dispersion depends on several meteorological factors. Wind speed and direction determine the affected area, but the influence of the surface topography, which creates local barriers and determines the direction of pollution spread, is also crucial (Du, Wang and Wang, 2022). Precipitation has an important effect on the “washing out” of particles, areas with regular rainfall tend to have cleaner air, while arid and semi-arid areas are, on the other side, more susceptible to greater pollution (Tiwary and Williams, 2019). Surface watering is purposely used in some quarries to reduce pollution (Gautam and B. Bolia, 2020). It has been found that it is possible to reduce emissions by 50% by water sprinkling every hour (Du, Wang and Wang, 2022).

3.2.4 Impact of PM pollution

A wide range of organisms are affected by air dust pollution. According to several studies (Tiwary and Williams, 2019; Gokul *et al.*, 2023; Yu and Zahidi, 2023), settled dust on plant leaves can affect photosynthesis, respiration and evapotranspiration processes that leads to reducing vegetation health and productivity. This has implications for agriculture, as affected plants produce less growth and even the nutritional value of the final product is reduced. A secondary problem is the chemical composition of the dust particles, which can contain copper, manganese, cobalt, zinc, or other metals, which on one side are necessary trace elements that are essential for plant growth, but at high levels, they can be toxic (Yu and Zahidi, 2023).

PM pollution also has harmful effects on humans. The problem is the size of these particles, which are small enough to enter the respiratory tract and even further into the bloodstream, etc., where they can settle and accumulate. Dust pollution affects workers as well as the general public, with the elderly, children and people with other medical conditions more likely to be affected (Tiwary and Williams, 2019; Gautam and B. Bolia, 2020).

The main effect of airborne dust pollution is on the respiratory system, where even short exposures can cause irritation of the eyes, skin and respiratory tract, resulting in coughing or asthma attacks. Long-term exposure or high levels of pollution can lead to respiratory diseases such as reduced lung function or pneumonia, heart problems or even cancer, mainly affecting the lungs and respiratory tract. With high exposure to the smallest particles, the effects on blood circulation and brain function increase (Choudhury, Gordian and Morris, 1997). Several studies (Choudhury, Gordian and Morris, 1997; Gautam and B. Bolia, 2020; Yu and Zahidi, 2023) show that high levels of particles in air lead to increased morbidity and mortality.

On a global scale, high concentrations of aerosols, which are by mass mainly dominated by dust, reflect solar and terrestrial radiation, affecting the energy budget of the planet, with consequent effects on air temperature and other meteorological components (Klingmüller *et al.*, 2019). In addition, these particles act as ice and cloud condensation nuclei and their concentration affects the formation of precipitation (Xia *et al.*, 2022).

All this has socio-economic implications for the whole community. Subsequent problems are seen in reduced visibility, lowered economy, less manpower, increased need for medical facilities etc. (Gautam and B. Bolia, 2020).

3.3 PM monitoring

Since it is known how PM pollution can affect our lives in many ways, it is important to know the amount of particles that are dispersed in the air. There are several methods for monitoring PM, which can be divided into in-situ methods and remote sensing techniques.

3.3.1 In-situ monitoring

The simplest way to analyse pollution is to take air samples. In-situ monitoring provides information about the composition of the air at a point in space, usually by taking samples of the known a volume of the air to be analysed later in the laboratory, or by taking the whole monitoring instrument to the desired location and getting immediate results. The first approach is more suitable for research and locations where continuous monitoring is not required. More commonly, monitoring instruments are used that remain in place for long periods of time, providing time series as a result (Burrows, Platt and Borrell, 2011).

Monitoring stations are usually managed by the local meteorological office or another group with an interest in this issue at the site. The advantages of in-situ monitoring are in the accuracy of the results, the speed with which they can be processed and, in the case of long-term measurements, the generation of time series that can be used to determine the temporal evolution of pollution at the site. The disadvantages are

that they are spatially limited, and it is difficult to monitor large or remote areas and areas covered by water (Burrows, Platt and Borrell, 2011).

3.3.1.1 Filtration based methods

The simplest monitoring methods are based on gravimetric filtration of air samples passing through a filter with a given gap size, which should select the desired particles, which are additionally weighted. These methods are simple and cheap, but their problems lie in the collection of particles, which in itself alters the air flow through the filter and reduces the resulting efficiency (Tiwary and Williams, 2019).

3.3.1.2 Optical methods

Optical particle monitoring methods use the scattering and absorption properties of particles to measure concentration. The size and coarseness of the particles determine how the light is scattered (Rodríguez, Alastuey and Querol, 2012). Common instruments that use scattering to monitor dust concentrations include nephelometers. These measure the scattered light waves from the air sample passing through a cylinder where multiple light waves illuminate the air stream at a given angle (Tiwary and Williams, 2019). The resulting quantification is made by comparing of these results with those obtained on the clear (filtered, particles-free) air (Rodríguez, Alastuey and Querol, 2012).

3.3.2 Remote sensing techniques

All measurement methods that do not involve direct contact are referred to as remote sensing (Congalton, 2010). In the case of dust monitoring, this means obtaining the physical properties of the scene. This is done by measuring the emitted or reflected radiation from the scene, usually captured by sensors on satellites (Burrows, Platt and Borrell, 2011).

These sensors can be either passive or active. Active systems introduce specific energy into the measurement from the instrument itself and measure its reflection, in this group are lidars and radars. Passive systems use external energy reflected from the sun or emitted directly from the earth ground, these are known as optical systems (Castellanos *et al.*, 2024).

Spatio-temporal data availability depends on the orbits and viewing geometry. All types are used, from lower near-polar orbits, which typically have higher spatial resolution but temporal resolution in the range of hours, to data from geospatial orbits that can provide results every few minutes (Randall, 2008).

3.3.2.1 Aerosol optical depth

Aerosol optical depth (AOD) or aerosol optical thickness (AOT) is a dimensionless unit that measures the rate at which aerosol particles (dust, smoke, salt, etc.) affect the passage of solar radiation through the atmosphere by scattering and absorbing it. Reflected solar radiation from the real atmosphere is measured by satellites as Top of Atmosphere (TOA) reflectance for specific wavelengths, mostly used is 550 nm. The problem is that a large part of the TOA reflectance is the contribution of surface reflectance. To remove this influence, correction methods such as the Deep Blue (DB) or Dark Target (DT) algorithms for different surfaces are used and these values are later compared with simulated radiation from the clear atmosphere. These correction methods are described in more detail e.g. in Wei *et al.*, 2020. There are several instruments on board different satellites that measure AOD, for example in this work AOD at 550 nm was retrieved from the MODIS instrument on board NASA's Terra and Aqua satellites. Other satellites providing AOD measurements include CALIOP, VIIRS and others (Wei *et al.*, 2020).

AOD can also be measured the other way round, from ground-based photometers. One of the best known is the AERONET network, which has its photometers all over the world. AERONET is mainly used to validate other products because they have limited spatial coverage (Castellanos *et al.*, 2024).

3.3.2.2 Dust indexes and band ratios

RGB composites, band ratios or indexes are used to classify the aerosol type. Against AOD are in this approach used several channels where are observed changes in spectral reflectance based on the material, its size, coarseness and also its concentration, when higher concentrations of pollutants are easier to detect than low (Randall, 2008). The distinction between water and dust clouds is usually based on the high reflectance of water clouds in the visible bands (0.4 to 0.7 μm) and their low reflectance in the near-infrared bands (decreasing brightness temperature from 10 μm to 12 μm), whereas the opposite is usually true for dust (increasing brightness temperature from 10 μm to 12 μm). The most commonly used wavelengths for dust monitoring are around 0.65, 0.86, 2.3, 3.7, 8.6, 9.6, 11 and 12 μm (Li *et al.*, 2021; Liu and Liu, no date).

The Brightness Temperature Difference (BTD) technique (or sometimes called the Split Window technique) uses the mentioned wavelengths from 10 μm to 12 μm where silicates, which typically make up a large component of dust, create a "V" curve in the spectral profile. This is a relatively effective way of distinguishing clouds that behave in the opposite way in this part of the spectrum. This approach is problematic for distinguishing dust over bright surfaces such as deserts, where another additional combination with other bands is used for more robust results (Li *et al.*, 2021).

BTDs form the basis for dust indices that are more complex and developed for specific sensors. Some of the most used are, for example, The Normalised Difference Dust Index (NDDI), which is more suitable for non-desert areas (Yue *et al.*, 2017), the

Middle East Dust Index (MEDI), which was developed for dust areas around the Arabian Peninsula, or indexes such as the Thermal Infrared Dust Index (TDI), which are extended by coefficients and thresholds for better estimation results (Li *et al.*, 2021). Formulas for these indexes are as follows:

$$NDDI = \frac{BT_{0.469\mu\text{m}} - BT_{2.13\mu\text{m}}}{BT_{0.469\mu\text{m}} + BT_{2.13\mu\text{m}}}$$

$$MEDI = \frac{BT_{11\mu\text{m}} - BT_{8.5\mu\text{m}}}{BT_{12\mu\text{m}} - BT_{8.5\mu\text{m}}}$$

$$TDI = C_0 + C_1 \times BT_{3.7\mu\text{m}} + C_2 \times BT_{9.7\mu\text{m}} + C_3 \times BT_{11\mu\text{m}} + C_4 \times BT_{12\mu\text{m}}$$

where coefficients $C_{0,1,2,3,4}$ are estimated for each case separately, from regression relationships between AOD and BTs (Li *et al.*, 2021).

For easy visual detection of dust plumes, optical data are used in RGB false colour composites. Even in these composites, BTD is often used. For example, the Dust RGB Imaging product from the SEVIRI sensor on board the Meteosat satellite uses these band differences:

Red: $12.0\mu\text{m} - 10.8\mu\text{m}$

Green: $10.8\mu\text{m} - 8.7\mu\text{m}$

Blue: $10.8\mu\text{m}$

From this composite, dust appears in pink/magenta colours based on particle concentration and time of day (AlNasser and Entekhabi, 2023).

3.3.2.3 Lidar measurements of atmospheric profile

Lidar can be used to observe particle distribution profiles in the atmosphere. Lidar uses generated laser pulses of known wavelength to detect objects in its path from the time of backscattered signal retrieval (Castellanos *et al.*, 2024). In this way, it is possible to construct a profile of the atmosphere at a given location. The disadvantage is that the footprint of this beam is narrow, and it cannot easily cover large areas. One of the best known lidar instruments for obtaining aerosol profiles is e.g. CALIOP (Randall, 2008).

3.3.3 Modelling and forecasting of dust pollution

For complex monitoring, a combination of approaches is usually used. These models integrate multiple data sources, such as remote sensing observations, in-situ measurements, and other meteorological inputs to simulate the transport of aerosols in the atmosphere (El-Harbawi, 2013).

Data assimilation models use a combination of observations and numerical models to determine the areal state of pollution. These observations are usually in-situ measurements but can also be remote sensing data used in the models (El-Harbawi,

2013). With the input data, source characteristics (point, line and areal sources known to contribute to PM pollution) are included in calculations with known chemical, transport and leaching parameters of these pollutants to achieve most relevant results with full spatial coverage (van Aalst *et al.*, 1998). This approach is particularly useful for short-term prediction, providing a near real-time assessment of PM concentration for upcoming hours and days (San José *et al.*, 2008).

A key example of this approach is the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) which integrates satellite monitoring with in-situ data and numerical models used for air quality analysis and forecasting (Garrigues *et al.*, 2022). These data are used later in this work.

For long-term forecasting, statistical and machine learning models that use historical data are more suitable. Statistical models, such as SARIMA (Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average) and Prophet, are commonly used for time series forecasting. These methods analyse historical data to identify trends and seasonal patterns, allowing extrapolation into the future (Parasyris *et al.*, 2022). The disadvantage of these approaches is that they cannot predict periods of unusual concentrations and conditions that deviate from the historical record (Baklanov and Zhang, 2020).

More advanced capabilities are provided by machine learning models, which can use multiple input variables. These integrate data and other meteorological parameters as an input to algorithms that allow computers to learn data patterns to improve accuracy (Obisesan, 2024). Models such as XGBoost, Random Forest that are based on decision trees, or other artificial neural networks (ANN), are widely used (Segovia *et al.*, 2023; Zhang *et al.*, 2024).

The quality of the forecast depends on the quality of the data itself, as some pollutants are more predictable than others. The location, the level of emission inventories and the meteorological conditions also play a role in the prediction possibilities. Forecasts and models are provided by local meteorological services or other institutions and organisations specialising in air pollution, where the data are stored and released to the public. In general, air pollution models are used not only for air quality forecasting, but also for policy and decision making, and for research in climate studies (San José *et al.*, 2008).

3.4 Limits, legislative and standards

As the long-term goal is to reduce PM in the air, there are set limits and standards to follow. Currently, the European Union has *Directive 2008/50/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 May 2008 on ambient air quality and cleaner air for Europe*, 2008, which sets limit values for pollutants to protect against their known effects. The 24-hour average limit value for PM₁₀ is set at 50 µg/m³, which shouldn't be exceeded more than 35 times a year, while the annual average should not exceed

40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Both Greece and Finland follow these directions. The World Health Organisation (WHO) sets the 24-hour mean the same as EU directive at 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The annual average is set at a few levels of the interim target. The lowest level of pollution for which there is evidence of an association with mortality from long-term exposure is set at 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ as the Air Quality Guideline (AQG). There are three further interim targets with increasing mortality risk, 30, 50 and the highest is 70 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ as an annual mean, with the highest interim target (70 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) being associated with about 15% higher mortality risk relative to the AQG (*WHO Global Air Quality Guidelines: Particulate Matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), Ozone, Nitrogen Dioxide, Sulfur Dioxide and Carbon Monoxide*. 1st ed, 2021).

4 Characteristics of the study area

This study focuses on two different localities, where surrounding area is affected by open pit mining activities, in Greece, and in Finland.

4.1 Greece

The first area of interest is in the north-east of the Chalkidiki peninsula in Greece. There are located three open pit mining sites, operated by Hellas Gold Company, a subsidiary of Eldorado Gold Corporation. The history of mining in this area is traced back to ancient Greece, but Hellas Gold Company has been continuing in this tradition since 2004. Precious metals such as copper, gold, silver, lead and zinc are extracted from the Olympias, Skouriers and Stratoni mines (*Kassandra Mines - Hellas Gold, 2024*).

Mining sites are in distances from 1 to 5 km from populated areas. The total area of interest for our study is approximately 300 square kilometres (see *Fig.1.*).

Area of interest - Chalkidki Peninsula

Fig. 1. Area of interest - Chalkidiki peninsula, Greece

4.2 Finland

The second area is in south-eastern Finland, in Ihalainen, near the city of Lappeenranta where, in close proximity, is operated a quarry by Nordkalk Corporation, a subsidiary of UK-based SigmaRoc PLC. Nordkalk started mining activities in this area in 1910. The main materials extracted are limestone, limestone powder and wollastonite, which is the only one of its kind mined here in Europe (*Lappeenranta*, 2024).

In this case, area of interest covers around 600 square kilometres (see *Fig.2.*).

Fig. 2. Area of interest - Lappeenranta, Finland

5 Data and Methodology

This chapter summarises the data and procedures used to achieve the objectives of this thesis.

5.1 Datasets

5.1.1 In-situ data

In-situ measurements are an important source of information about the pollution situation at a precise time and place. The data are often long time series with periodic measurements over a day that allow us to analyse evolution and trends over time. These measurements are often used by governments or companies as a tool to monitor the overall situation and to quickly initiate certain actions when limits are exceeded. The second important role of in-situ measurements is to evaluate data obtained by other methods, in this case, remote sensing data. The disadvantage of this method is the lack of spatial variability, since the pollution in question is a continuous variable that changes rapidly in three-dimensional space due to the surrounding conditions.

5.1.1.1 Greece

At the Chalkidiki site, pollution data were obtained from Hellas Gold's environmental platform, available at: <https://environmental.hellas-gold.com/>. The platform provides measurements from mines and the surrounding environment of potential pollution from mining activities. In this case, we focus on dust pollution, but there are many more measurements of water quality, noise or vibrations available.

The data used in this study are measurements of dust in residential areas, specifically the PM10 variable, taken at 12 locations (see *Fig. 3.*). The time range is from June 2015, when the first stations started measuring, to August 2024. Values are available for each hour.

AOI Chalkidiki - IN-SITU monitoring stations

Fig. 3. Locations of in-situ monitoring stations at Chalkidiki locality

5.1.1.2 Finland

In Finland, measurements of particular pollutants are provided by the Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI). There are seven monitoring stations in Lappeenranta (see Fig. 4.), from which are five suitable for our case. The FMI provides hourly measurements of PM10 and other pollutants (PM25, carbon monoxide, ozone, nitrogen dioxide etc.) on a download page, available at: <https://en.ilmatieteenlaitos.fi/download-observations>. Data were collected from January 2013 to August 2024, based on the commissioning of individual stations.

AOI Lappeenranta - IN-SITU monitoring stations

Fig. 4. Locations of in-situ monitoring stations at Ihalainen, Lappeenranta

5.1.2 Remote sensing data and products

Compared to in-situ measurements, remote sensing data and products can provide greater spatial coverage with great temporal resolution over long periods of time and are even suitable for retrospective analysis. When open data are used, the financial cost of monitoring is low. On the other hand, the disadvantages of these data can be in low spatial resolution and in their inability to capture local extremes. Another problem is the influence of local weather and cloud cover in the upper atmosphere.

5.1.2.1 CAMS data product

The Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) is a part of the Copernicus European Union's Earth observation programme. Copernicus provides products based on satellite observations, in-situ measurements and data modelling and is implemented by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) (*Copernicus*, 2024).

For the purposes of this work, the CAMS European air quality reanalysis and analysis datasets have been selected. Both of these datasets are produced as an ensemble product of eleven numerical models developed all across Europe where each of them uses satellite observations and in-situ data for the output product. Analysis data are provided in near-real time and are available as a three-year rolling archive. Reanalysis data, on the other hand, are available as a complete historical archive as an annual file. These released with a two-year delay due to additional quality control, back-testing, and validation with a wider set of in-situ observations.

These data are provided as netCDF multidimensional grids, directly from the atmosphere datastore or via API, with spatial resolution of $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ (approximately 10 km x 10 km) per pixel. Data are stored in hourly temporal resolution and are provided in several levels of vertical coverage (*CAMS European air quality forecasts*, 2024).

The selected variable for this work is the same as in the in-situ data, PM10 at surface level, and was obtained to match the in-situ temporal and spatial coverage.

5.1.2.2 MODIS

The Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer, known as MODIS, is a sensor on NASA's Aqua and Terra satellites designed to observe the Earth, model climate change or human impact, and better understand ecological, hydrological and meteorological conditions (Lindsey and Herring, no date). There are 4 overpasses per day at each locality, approximately at 10:30 on the Terra descending node, at 13:30 on the Aqua ascending node and then nighttime overpasses that primarily contribute to thermal observations. Modis acquires data in 36 spectral bands with resolutions ranging from 250 metres to 1 kilometre, from which several additional products are produced (Randall, 2008).

The products chosen for this case are aerosol optical depth (AOD) at 0.55 μm data with different processing and resolution compared in *Tab.1*.

product	spatial resolution	temporal resolution	description
MOD04_L2 / MYD04_L2	10 km	4 times in a day	Aerosol Optical Thickness at 0.55 μm for both Ocean (best) and Land (corrected) with best quality data (QA Confidence Flag = 3)
MOD04_3K / MYD04_3K	3 km	4 times in a day	Aerosol Optical Thickness at 0.55 μm for both Ocean (best) and Land (corrected) with best quality data (QA Confidence Flag = 3)
MCD19A2.0 61	1 km	daily	Aerosol optical Depth at 0.55 μm , gridded Level 2 aerosol data derived from the Multi-Angle Implementation of Atmospheric Correction (MAIAC) (Lyapustin and Wang, no date)

Tab. 1. MODIS AOD products

5.2 Data processing

5.2.1 Data acquisition and preprocessing

Both in-situ data were downloaded directly from the websites mentioned earlier in chapter 5.1 *Datasets*, from Hellas Gold's environmental platform and the Finnish Meteorological Institute. Data for the Chalkidiki locality were collected from 2015 to 2024, while data for the Finnish locality covered the period from 2013 to 2024.

Remote sensing products were obtained and processed using python. CAMS data were accessed using the Climate Data Store Application Program Interface (CDSAPI) package via a Google Colab Jupyter notebook. The CDSAPI requires the URL of the Copernicus Atmosphere Data Store along with a unique authentication key, which is provided to users when they log into their account.

MODIS Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) data have been accessed through NASA's Earthdata platform using the earthaccess library in Colab. Access to Earthdata requires a registered username and password.

Additional data retrieval settings are provided in *Appendix 1*.

Python scripts were used to first convert all data to UTC to ensure temporal consistency. To standardise the temporal resolution across all datasets, the daily medians were created and stored as representative values extracted from pixels corresponding spatially to the locations of the measuring stations. As there were three MODIS datasets mentioned, these were at first obtained for the Chalkidiki locality for 2015 and from the correlation analysis (*chapter 6.3 correlation analysis*) the 3 km product was selected and further used. As a result, there is a time series table containing values for each station from the in-situ, CAMS and MODIS datasets. Although the in-situ and MODIS data contain NA values, it was decided to leave them as they are and not to interpolate them due to the general nature of these data, which change rapidly and independently over time. In addition, CAMS data were stored as daily rasters and organised into monthly multidimensional files.

5.2.2 Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis of in-situ time series data was carried out for the overall study and description of PM10 pollution at the monitoring stations in both locations, Greece and Finland, and for their comparison. In addition, two remote sensing data products were compared with the in-situ data and their applicability for PM pollution monitoring was investigated.

The following statistical analyses were performed in the R programming language in RStudio.

5.2.2.1 Primary descriptive statistics

To describe the in-situ data, histograms and box plots were generated for each station to provide general information about each time series data. The R describe function was used to generate some descriptive parameters such as minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation, etc.

5.2.2.2 Analysis of station specificity

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed on the in-situ time series data to identify similarities between individual station measurements. PCA is a commonly used method to simplify and reduce the dimensionality of data while preserving significant patterns. This is achieved by transforming the original variables into new, uncorrelated variables. These new components always capture as much of the variability as possible, with the first component explaining most of the variance, the second a little less, and so on. Secondly calculated annual and monthly means were visualised to provide clear comparison and validation of the PCA results.

5.2.2.3 Correlation analysis

As there is no visible normal distribution of the data from the histograms, Spearman correlations were performed to observe the strength of the relationships in all datasets. The Spearman correlation measures the strength and direction of the relationship between two values and is also suitable for non-linear relationships. The coefficient

takes values from -1 to 1, with $r_s = 1$ indicating a perfectly positive relationship, $r_s = -1$ indicating a perfectly negative relationship and $r_s = 0$ indicating no relationship.

First, three MODIS datasets were compared with in-situ data at the Chalkidiki site in 2015 to determine which resolution was most appropriate for this analysis. The dataset with the strongest correlation was further analysed together with CAMS and in-situ data over the entire study period for both sites.

5.2.2.4 Trends and Seasonality analysis

In order to examine the long-term temporal dynamics of the time series, the data have been decomposed into trend, seasonal and residual variables with a seasonal trend decomposition using locally estimated scatterplot smoothing (STL decomposition). This allows us to observe long-term trends and periodic fluctuations in our data and provides a different perspective on the differences between the datasets. CAMS and in-situ datasets were used for this purpose. For this purpose, the in-situ data were clustered to the CAMS resolution based on "pixel containing" means.

5.2.2.5 Time series modelling and forecasting

In addition, as the seasonal decomposition focuses on the past, some modelling techniques were undertaken to provide a brief overview of future trends in PM pollution. Two models or techniques were investigated in R programming language for predicting seasonal trends - Prophet and Bayesian Structural Time Series (BSTS).

Prophet is an automated forecasting procedure developed by Facebook (now Meta). The model combines additive regression with linear or logistic trend and seasonality (yearly, monthly, weekly...). Prophet works best with highly seasonal data over a long time series and is even robust to missing values. It is easy to implement and does not require large parameter settings (Taylor and Letham, 2021). BSTS works similarly using the decomposition of time series data into trend and seasonal variables that are extended for forecasting purposes. On the other side from Prophet, BSTS requires more setting parameters, is more flexible to seasonality settings and is even possible to use more regressor parameters. BSTS does not support missing values in a time series data (Scott, 2024).

Both methods were trained on the data until the end of 2023 and validated on 8 months of 2024 data. Forecasts were extended to the end of 2025. The Prophet models were implemented using the Prophet package with default seasonal settings. Daily and monthly values from CAMS and in-situ data were used for the analysis. BSTS, from the package of the same name, was used with a semi-local linear trend specification, 12 seasons and 1000 iterations on CAMS monthly data, as it doesn't support NA values in the training dataset.

For short-term prediction, XGBoost (Extreme Gradient Boosting) and Random Forest were investigated.

XGBoost is an efficient machine learning algorithm in the gradient boosting framework. The algorithm is based on parallel tree boosting, where each decision tree

tries to learn from the mistakes made in the previous trees and thus provide better accuracy. Parallel computing makes this method fast and suitable for use on large datasets (*XGBoost Documentation*, 2025). Random forest is also based on decision trees, but unlike the XGBoost, these are trained on random samples from the training dataset. The output prediction is given as the average of the whole forest (Breiman *et al.*, 2024).

In these cases, daily CAMS data were used and the distribution to the training and validation sets was the same as in the previous. The RandomForest package was used with cross-validation on 500 trees with node size 10. XGBoost, from xgboost package, were used with parameters of 8 lags, on gbtrees booster with maxdepth of 5 and 0.1 eta. Since XGBoost is based on lagged values, in order to extend the prediction to a longer scale, beyond the available data horizon, an iterative procedure defined for 90 days with the same parameters as simple XGBoost was also studied. The new predicted value was there recursively added as an input for the next day's prediction. All forecasts were evaluated using metrics like root mean square error (RMSE), correlation (r) or mean absolute error (mae) on validation datasets.

Additional settings for each prediction model are provided in R code in *Appendix 2*.

5.2.3 Spatial data analysis

CAMS data were also stored as daily median grids in the multidimensional monthly files. For further visualisation, these data were aggregated via python scripts into monthly and annual mean rasters on both localities for the whole temporal range to analyse some spatio-temporal relationships.

Methodology overview is provided in followed *Fig. 5*.

Fig. 5. Graphical methodology overview

6 Results

6.1 Descriptive statistics of in-situ data

The description in *Tab. 2.* provides information of the in-situ data at both study areas. The values show variability, with mean concentrations ranging from 8.19 to 40.03 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and standard deviations ranging from 6.16 to 35.41 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, indicating differences in pollution levels between sites, with higher overall values being observed at the Chalkidiki site.

Most stations show positive skewness (1.52 to 4.35) and high kurtosis (2.83 to 49.53), indicating that the distributions are right-skewed with strong tails, meaning that extreme pollution events occur occasionally. The medians are consistently lower than the means, confirming this skewness.

Descriptive statistics of in-situ PM10 data ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)

locality	number of values	mean value	standart deviation	median	min	max	range (min - max)	skew	kurtosis
Chalkidiki									
ins_MAM21	2455	17,47	9,36	15,6	1,8	167,45	165,65	3,45	32,59
ins_MAM22	2448	15,55	9,41	13,79	1,26	165,86	164,6	3,59	33,7
ins_MAM23	2342	16,16	9,09	14,54	0	155,61	155,61	3,16	29,08
ins_MAM24	2151	15,31	9,6	13,47	1,28	157,99	156,71	3,11	26,61
ins_MAM25	3346	24,23	10,99	22,42	0	215,72	215,72	2,8	31,42
ins_MAM26	3345	18,35	9,49	16,75	0	163,71	163,71	2,37	20,22
ins_OAM31	2367	17,55	8,4	16,47	2,07	171,02	168,95	3,73	49,53
ins_OAM32	2445	27,94	16,04	23,32	3,4	198,06	194,65	1,73	6,61
ins_SAM31	2396	17,74	10,76	14,96	1,11	117,81	116,7	2,16	8,78
ins_SAM32	2382	36,86	35,41	24,97	5,36	347,11	341,74	3,26	14,41
ins_SAM33	2395	26,79	12,54	23,95	0,12	132,92	132,8	1,52	5,06
ins_SAM34	2424	40,03	31,17	27,59	4,4	218,2	213,8	1,67	2,83
Ihalainen									
ins_IH	4219	10,83	8,56	8,4	0,6	130,5	129,9	4,09	32,84
ins_JOUK	4132	9,22	7,6	7,3	0	92,05	92,05	2,83	14,17
ins_LAU	3512	9,76	7,67	8	0,3	105,5	105,2	4,35	32,34
ins_OJAT	950	8,19	6,16	6,55	0,6	50,8	50,2	2,03	5,91
ins_KES4	4240	11,47	9,97	8,62	1	132	131	4,23	31,37

Tab. 2. Descriptive statistics of in-situ data from Chalkidiki and Ihalainen

Visualised box plots (see Fig. 6. and Fig. 9.) and histograms (see Fig. 6. and Fig. 8.) confirmed high variability in each dataset, with many outlier values observed.

Fig. 6. Histogram of in-situ values at Chalkidiki

Fig. 7. Boxplot of in-situ values at Chalkidiki

Fig. 8. Histogram of in-situ values at Ihalainen

Fig. 9. Boxplot of in-situ values at Ihalainen

6.2 Stations specificity analysis

6.2.1 Principal components analysis of stations data

Principal component analysis (PCA) of the in-situ data provided the station-specific insights for each station. Visualised are PCA plots of the first two components for both localities, which contain points from each measurement at the station in time. The direction and length of the arrows indicate how the original variables contribute to these principal components and indicate the variation between datasets.

More diversity is observed in the data from the Chalkidiki site. Three groups of stations are visible, more or less in the main direction of the first component, and then another three stations that stand out as different in terms of data characteristics. Station OAM32 shows a stronger negative direction on the second component, while SAM32 and SAM34 show almost opposite directions (see *Fig. 10.*). The data of the Ihalainen stations are less diversified on the second component scale. The stations JOUK and OJAT stand out from IH, KES4 and LAU (see *Fig. 11.*).

Fig. 10. PCA analysis of in-situ data at Chalkidiki

Fig. 11. PCA analysis of locations data at Ihalainen

6.2.2 Visualisation of annual and monthly averages

The visualised annual averages of the in-situ data provide an overview of the overall trends in PM pollution at each station location. Although the AOI in Chalkidiki is smaller than in Ihalainen, there is a much wider range of annual values over the whole monitoring period. PM₁₀ pollution varies from 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to over 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, with the highest values in 2020 at SAM34 and SAM32. Apart from these two, the sites show a more or less permanent state (see *Fig. 12.*). On the other hand, the annual values of PM₁₀ at the Ihalainen monitoring stations range from 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The trend is clearly downwards, with a maximum in 2014. Higher values are observed at the KES4 and IH sites (see *Fig. 13.*).

AOI Chalkidiki - IN-SITU monitoring stations

(a)

IN-SITU annual means Chalkidiki

(b)

Fig. 12. (a) AOI Chalkidiki - in-situ stations, (b) Chalkidiki in-situ annual means for 2015-2024

AOI Lappeenranta - IN-SITU monitoring stations (a)

IN-SITU annual means Ihalainen (b)

Fig. 13. (a) AOI Ihalainen - in-situ stations, (b) In-situ annual means at Ihalainen for 2013-2024

As with the annual data, the monthly mean plots also show less diversity at the Ihalainen sites. The annual cycles are similar at all stations, with OJAT and JOUK showing higher values, especially in the earlier years up to 2020 (see Fig. 15.). At Chalkidiki sites, extremely high values are repeatedly observed at SAM32 and SAM34 in winter and at OAM32 in summer (see Fig. 14.). The presumed reasons for this are their location in residential areas, where heating activity could lead

to higher emissions, and the location of OAM32 on the coast where pollution can contain sand and salt particles.

Fig. 14. in-situ monthly means at Chalkidiki for 2015-2024

Fig. 15. in-situ monthly means at Ihalainen for 2013-2024

Another view is provided by seasonal graphs, which visualise the means of each station in months through years. Three extremes are visible at the Chalkidiki site mentioned above (see Fig. 16 (a)). By zooming in on the graph, it is possible to see

lower values in the winter (wet) season from November to March and higher values in the summer (dry) season with a peak in August (see Fig. 16 (b)). However, stations such as MAM25 and MAM26 show similar seasonality to SAM32 and SAM34, i.e. maximum values in winter, as they are also located in residential areas.

Fig. 16. (a) Stations mean seasonality through years 2015-2023 at Chlkidiki locality, (b) seasonality - zoomed in

The seasonality of the Ihalainen in-situ data is quite different. Minimum values are also observed in winter, from October to February, with airborne PM10 concentrations increasing to their maximum in April (see Fig. 17.). This increase is probably due to lower precipitation in the spring months.

Fig. 17. Stations mean seasonality through years 2013-2023 at Ihalainen

6.3 Correlations of CAMS and MODIS data with in-situ datasets

Examination of three AOD-MODIS data products for 2015 revealed poor correlations with in-situ measurements. Since MODIS data are challenging due to missing values, the highest available measurements provided a 3 km resolution product (61.9% missing values), which has even the best correlation results, but these are still inadequate. Depending on the location, they vary around $r_s \approx 0.35$ with MOD04_3K, $r_s \approx 0.31$ with MOD04_L2 and $r_s \approx 0.18$ with the MCD19a2.061 datasets on Chalkidiki locality for 2015 period. Given these results, the MOD04_3K data are additionally used, but only as a supplementary.

The analysis over the whole temporal range shows differences between both sites and even between stations. Results at the Chalkidiki site are more diverse. The correlation of CAMS data ranges from $r_s \approx 0.3$ at SAM32 and SAM34 locations, to the best results of $r_s \approx 0.8$ at MAM21, MAM22, MAM23 and MAM24 localities. Results

6.4 Trends and seasonality

This chapter was partially discussed in the previous one, but here the focus is on seasonal decomposition on both clustered in-situ and CAMS data to trend, seasonal variable and residuals. In this analysis were intentionally omitted data from three stations with extreme values.

A comparison of the trend components from all datasets for both sites in Greece and Finland shows that the derived values from CAMS data are overall lower, more balanced and similar to each other. This is determined by the pixel size, where all local maxima and minima are merged to a pixel size of 10x10 km. In the long term, data from all stations in both datasets show a balanced, rather decreasing trend in PM10 pollution. The Finnish data achieve smaller differences and overall lower values than in Greece, more similarity is observed after 2020. Improvement of conditions is there more visible, especially from in-situ data. Comparison of these is in following *Fig. 18.* and *Fig. 19.*

Fig. 18. PM 10 Trends from CAMS and in-situ data at Chalkidiki locality for 2015-2024

STL Decomposition - Trend variables, Ihalainen

Fig. 19. PM 10 Trends from CAMS and in-situ data at Ihalainen locality for 2013-2024

The in-situ data also show higher values for the seasonal variable. At the Ihalainen site the distribution from both datasets corresponds to maxima in early spring. Minima fluctuate slightly different but in both datasets are in autumn and winter (see Fig. 22. and 23.). The seasonality at the Chalkidiki sites is more complicated. CAMS data show a similar seasonality as in Finland, with higher values in spring and lower values in winter. In-situ data are much more variable as described in the previous chapter. The seasonality of MAM21-24, OAM31 fluctuates between summer peaks and lower values in winter, just like the CAMS data, the other stations give almost opposite results (see Fig. 20. and 21.).

STL Decomposition - CAMS Seasonal variables, Chalkidiki

Fig. 20. CAMS seasonal variables at Chalkidiki

STL Decomposition - IN-SITU Seasonal variables, Chalkidiki

Fig. 21. in-situ seasonal variables at Chalkidiki

STL Decomposition - CAMS Seasonal variables, Ihalainen

Fig. 22. CAMS seasonal variables at Ihalainen

STL Decomposition - IN-SITU Seasonal variable, Ihalainen

Fig. 23. in-situ seasonal variables at Ihalainen

6.5 Spatio-temporal analysis

6.5.1 Long-term spatio-temporal analysis

At both study sites, annual means provide a spatio-temporal picture of PM pollution across years. These represent smoothed long-term perspectives, highlighting more polluted areas in the whole temporal range across the AOI and providing another view of the annual means from *chapter 6.2.2*.

The most polluted years were in 2016 on the Chalkidiki peninsula, where annual means were above $16 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. From these, the north-eastern area of the AOI seems to be more polluted. Pollution at the locations of the monitoring stations is the lowest of the whole area (see *Fig. 24*).

At the Ihalainen site maximum values are observed in 2014. In contrast to Chalkidiki, peaks in this area are observed around monitoring stations in Lappeenranta. As this AOI is larger, another hotspot is observed at the nearby town Vyborg, which is even more polluted in some years (see *Fig. 25*).

Annual means of PM10 CAMS data in 2015-2023 at Chalkidiki

Fig. 24 - Annual means of PM10 CAMS data in 2015-2023 at Chalkidiki

Annual means of PM10 CAMS data in 2013-2023, Finland

Fig. 25 - Annual means of PM10 CAMS data in 2013-2023, Finland

6.5.2 Annual spatio-temporal analysis

From the monthly averages over the years, we can observe annual variations in PM pollution in our areas. In Chalkidiki the distribution of pollution is more balanced. Lower values are observed in the winter months, in December and January, where there is an immediate increase with a peak in April. Spatially, distribution varies slightly with higher values in the northern part of the area in winter months, in summer time higher values are more in the south-eastern corner of the AOI (see *Fig. 26.*).

Pollution at Ihalainen AOI is more variable with more difference between urban and natural areas. Peaks are observed in spring, February and March in urban areas. The lowest levels of PM are observed in the north-west of the monitoring stations (see *Fig. 27.*).

Monthly means of PM10 CAMS data across years 2015-2023 at Chalkidiki

Fig. 26 - Monthly means of PM10 CAMS data across years 2015-2023 at Chalkidiki

Monthly means of PM10 CAMS data across years 2013-2023, Finland

Fig. 27 - Monthly means of PM10 CAMS data across years 2013-2023, Finland

6.6 PM10 Time series modelling and forecasting

For long-term seasonality and trend predictions, Prophet and BSTS models were investigated. These were trained with the data from 2015 (2013 for Ihalainen) to the end of 2023 and validated with data from January to August 2024. Predictions were extended to the end of 2025. According to metrics made on validation datasets, Prophet provides slightly better results at Chalkidiki, but BSTS turns better at Ihalainen *Tab. 5*.

Locality	PROPHET			BSTS		
	RMSE	r	MAE	RMSE	r	MAE
Chalkidiki						
CAMS MAM21_24	1,681	0,31	1,337	1,695	0,262	1,368
CAMS MAM25_26	1,586	0,333	1,281	1,625	0,262	1,304
CAMS OAM31	1,691	0,31	1,353	1,72	0,333	1,383
CAMS SAM31	1,85	0,286	1,419	1,857	0,333	1,425
CAMS SAM33	1,928	0,381	1,479	1,945	0,214	1,521
Ihalainen						
CAMS IH	0,762	0,071	0,559	0,741	0,238	0,607
CAMS JOUK	1,187	0,048	0,992	0,918	0,048	0,784
CAMS KES4	0,827	0,31	0,618	0,711	0,19	0,594
CAMS LAU	0,648	0,262	0,544	0,7	0,167	0,582
CAMS OJAT	0,735	0,143	0,61	0,726	0,262	0,612

Tab. 5. Results on PROPHET and BSTS predictions on Jan. to Aug. 2024 validation dataset

As both models gave similar results, but only Prophet allowed NA values in the training dataset, this model was also used on the in-situ dataset for monthly and daily data. Another reason for choosing Prophet is the speed of the model and the lower computational effort.

The predicted trends in Chalkidiki are more or less stable at all sites in both datasets, except at site MAM25-26 where a steady decrease is observed after the year 2020. This drop is about $3\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in CAMS and $5\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in in-situ measurements. The trend for all Ihalainen stations is decreasing, which is more visible in the in-situ data. The decrease here is in the range from 5 to $10\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, in CAMS is it only from 1.5 to $2\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Only increasing trend is predicted at the OJAT locality, but this is due to the short training dataset, as these data are available from December 2021, so these results are not relevant. Predictions based on daily data show the same trend. Examples of Prophet predictions are shown in *Fig. 28.* and *29.*

Fig. 28. PROPHET prediction on CAMS IH monthly data

Fig. 29. PROPHET prediction on CAMS SAM31 monthly data

The XGBoost and Random Forest models turn out to be well suited to predicting a single subsequent value. That's because they rely on lagged features from historical data. For long-term predictions, iterative forecasting must be added, where the model uses its own previous predictions as input for subsequent steps. Unfortunately, this compounds errors and significantly increases uncertainty over time. This inherent

limitation makes these models less reliable for longer forecasting horizons without error propagation.

With keeping this in mind, XGBoost provides better results on the CAMS validation dataset, where it adapts better to fluctuations in PM pollution see *Tab. 6.* and *Fig. 30.* This model was also investigated with iteration for not depending on lagged values, results are visualised in *Fig. 31.*

Locality	XGBoost			Random Forest			Iterative XGBoost		
Chalkidiki	RMSE	r	MAE	RMSE	r	MAE	RMSE	r	MAE
CAMS MAM21_24	4,82	0,66	3,21	5,93	0,48	4,08	7,26	0,14	5,09
CAMS MAM25_26	5,24	0,6	3,46	5,99	0,51	3,98	7,08	0,16	4,95
CAMS OAM31	5,11	0,61	3,39	5,95	0,49	4,1	7,33	0,1	5,11
CAMS SAM31	5,19	0,61	3,38	5,98	0,5	4,04	7,39	5,21	
CAMS SAM33	5,43	0,61	3,51	6,25	0,51	4,17	7,77	0,08	5,42
Ihalainen									
CAMS IH	2,44	0,46	1,76	2,51	0,43	1,91	3,13	0,02	2,35
CAMS JOUK	2,38	0,46	1,7	2,44	0,47	1,83	3,1	-0,02	2,31
CAMS KES4	2,41	0,48	1,79	2,5	0,46	1,9	3,15	0	2,4
CAMS LAU	2,41	0,47	1,76	2,49	0,44	1,87	3,12	0,01	2,36
CAMS OJAT	2,45	0,46	1,75	2,49	0,44	1,87	3,19	0,01	2,39

Tab. 6. Validation metrics results on XGBoost, Random Forest and Iterative XGBoost predictions for Jan. to Aug. 2024

Predictions of XGBoost and Random Forest at SAM 31

Fig. 30. Predictions of XGBoost and Random Forest at SAM31 for Jan. to Aug 2024

XGBoost predictions at SAM31 for 2024 - Iterative Extension

Fig. 31. Iterative extension of XGBoost predictions at SAM31 from Jan. to Aug. 2024

7 Discussion

The main results of this analysis provide information on PM₁₀ pollution at two locations in Greece and Finland. Similarities are observed within the monitoring stations of each location and within the locations themselves. Subsequent analysis allows for comparison of different data sets.

From the correlation analysis it can be seen that the MODIS data gives poor results, with r_s varying around 0.35 depending on the location. These results are probably due to the high amount of missing values, which make up more than 60 % of all values. Reasons for missing values are cloud conditions and precipitation, as these data are based on optical properties of the atmosphere and clouds cover. These data are widely used in several studies (Randall, 2008; Zhang and Li, 2015; Lindsey and Herring, no date). From their results, it can be seen that they are preferably used at large scale analysis in arid areas such as desert regions, where they give better results at higher pollutant concentrations. The second reason why in-situ measurements are correlate poorly with MODIS AOD data is in the fact that MODIS provides information on the full column of the atmosphere, whereas in-situ measurements focus only on pollution close to the ground. This confirms that AOD data are more useful for monitoring large dust events and are less suitable for local, low pollution monitoring.

The more accurate results were observed for the CAMS dataset, where correlations with in-situ measurements reached $r_s = 0.8$ in the best cases. Similar results have been obtained, for example by Velea *et al.*, 2020, in their work on the locality in Romania. CAMS data seem to be a useful source for monitoring on larger areas, but it has to be kept in mind that the pixel size of about 10x10 km, does not provide information about local extremes. This is probably the reason why the correlations are lower in some anthropogenic areas or in places influenced by natural resources (like the Chalkidiki station OAM32 on the coast, where it is influenced by sand dust and salt aerosols).

PCA and visualisation of annual and monthly means gave a clear picture of each station and confirmed their diversity and difference in annual values. Although both sites are partly residential areas, their influence on the seasonality in Ihalainen is much smaller. The reason for this is probably in the exact location of the monitoring stations and the overall geographical context. The area of Chalkidiki is drier and more easily influenced by large dust storms from the African deserts. The topography may also have an influence, as the monitoring stations are located in the valleys, where the air flow directions are limited. The Ihalainen area, on the other hand, is more or less flat, which means that particles can easily be transported further by the wind, and precipitation is also more frequent. This is also reflected in the difference in annual values.

The trends show an improving tendency in PM pollution at both locations. The trends observed in the CAMS and in-situ datasets show similar progress at each station, but CAMS generally underestimates pollution levels. This is due to the resolution of the

CAMS data and its inability to deal with local extremes. This must be considered when using these data in analyses without the possibility of using in-situ data for validation.

Seasonal changes in CAMS and in situ differ from site to site. Again, CAMS provides information about the seasonal cycle that is present in most of the area of the site, and this is the reason why the seasonality at some stations gives completely different results in the two datasets. Seasonal maxima are generally observed in the summer months at Chalkidiki and in the spring at Ihalainen, in both cases as a result of the lowest precipitation of the year in these months.

The spatio-temporal analysis confirmed the seasonal trends on a spatial scale. It can be seen that at the Ihalainen site, anthropogenic areas are more visible as hotspots of PM pollution. The spatial distribution in Chalkidiki is less variable. This may be due to the local geography and topography mentioned above, but also to the extent of the AOI, which is much larger in Finland and therefore covers more differently used areas.

8 Conclusion

The objectives of the work have been achieved. Data from in-situ measurements and adequate satellite data products (CAMS PM10 and MODIS AOD) were obtained and aggregated for evaluation. Satellite data products were validated with in-situ measurements, and quantitative models were built for observational differences between locations and monitoring stations. Time series were extended to predict future trends using machine learning methods and statistical models.

Results of conducted analysis shows that CAMS PM10 product can be used as reliable source of information of PM pollution, especially in large areas where it is impossible to obtain values traditionally, even though it has its own specifics. Geography, topography of the locality and other local and global pollutant sources like transport or other industrial activities that influence local pollutant levels should be considered. In any case, some validation with local in-situ values should be carried out.

For long-term predictions, the Prophet model outperforms BSTS, while for short-term predictions XGBoost performs better than Random Forest.

Future work will focus on exploring potential of additional remote sensing data products (e.q. SEVIRI data) and more complex machine learning modelling techniques for more accurate results.

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Data sources

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List of figures

Fig. 1. Area of interest - Chalkidiki peninsula, Greece.....	19
Fig. 2. Area of interest - Lappeenranta, Finland	20
Fig. 3. Locations of in-situ monitoring stations at Chalkidiki locality	22
Fig. 4. Locations of in-situ monitoring stations at Ihalainen, Lappeenranta	22
Fig. 5. Graphical methodology overview.....	28
Fig. 6. Histogram of in-situ values at Chalkidiki.....	30
Fig. 7. Boxplot of in-situ values at Chalkidiki.....	30
Fig. 8. Histogram of in-situ values at Ihalainen.....	31
Fig. 9. Boxplot of in-situ values at Ihalainen.....	31
Fig. 10. PCA analysis of in-situ data at Chalkidiki.....	32
Fig. 11. PCA analysis of locations data at Ihalainen.....	33
Fig. 12. (a) AOI Chalkidiki - in-situ stations, (b) Chalkidiki in-situ annual means.....	34
Fig. 13. (a) AOI Ihalainen - in-situ stations, (b) In-situ annual means at Ihalainen ..	35
Fig. 14. in-situ monthly means at Chalkidiki	36
Fig. 15. in-situ monthly means at Ihalainen.....	36
Fig. 16. (a) Stations mean seasonality through years 2015-2023 at Chalkidiki locality, (b) seasonality - zoomed in	37
Fig. 17. Stations mean seasonality through years 2013-2023 at Ihalainen	38
Fig. 18. PM 10 Trends from CAMS and in-situ data at Chalkidiki locality	40
Fig. 19. PM 10 Trends from CAMS and in-situ data at Ihalainen locality	41
Fig. 20. CAMS seasonal variables at Chalkidiki	42
Fig. 21. in-situ seasonal variables at Chalkidiki	42
Fig. 22. CAMS seasonal variables at Ihalainen	43
Fig. 23. in-situ seasonal variables at Ihalainen	43
Fig. 24 - Annual means of PM10 CAMS data in 2015-2023 at Chalkidiki.....	45
Fig. 25 - Annual means of PM10 CAMS data in 2013-2023, Finland	46
Fig. 26 - Monthly means of PM10 CAMS data across years 2015-2023 at Chalkidiki	48
Fig. 27 - Monthly means of PM10 CAMS data across years 2013-2023, Finland....	49
Fig. 28. PROPHET prediction on CAMS IH data	51
Fig. 29. PROPHET prediction on CAMS SAM31 data.....	51
Fig. 30. Predictions of XGBoost and Random Forest at SAM31	52
Fig. 31. Iterative extension of XGBoost predictions at SAM31	53

List of tables

Tab. 1. MODIS AOD products	24
Tab. 2. Descriptive statistics of in-situ data from Chalkidiki and Ihalainen.....	29
Tab. 3. Correlations of CAMS, MODIS and in-situ data at Chalkidiki locality.....	39
Tab. 4. Correlations CAMS, MODIS and in-situ data at Ihalainen locality	39
Tab. 5. Results on PROPHET and BSTS predictions on Jan. to Aug. 2024 validation dataset.....	50
Tab. 6. Validation metrics results on XGBoost, Random Forest and Iterative XGBoost predictions for Jan. to Aug. 2024	52

Appendixes

Appendix 1. Python API for CAMS and MODIS data retrieval in google Colab.

Appendix 2. Additional settings for prediction models Prophet, BSTS, Random Forest and XGBoost in R programming language.

Appendix 1.

Python API for CAMS and MODIS data retrieval in google Colab.

CAMS

```
#authenticate
client = cdsapi.Client(url=URL, key=KEY)
client.retrieve(
    'cams-europe-air-quality-forecasts',
    {
        'variable': ['particulate_matter_10um'],
        'model': ['ensemble'],
        'level': ['0'],
        'date': f'{day_str}/{day_str}',
        'type': ['analysis'],
        'time': [
            "00:00", "01:00", "02:00",
            "03:00", "04:00", "05:00",
            "06:00", "07:00", "08:00",
            "09:00", "10:00", "11:00",
            "12:00", "13:00", "14:00",
            "15:00", "16:00", "17:00",
            "18:00", "19:00", "20:00",
            "21:00", "22:00", "23:00"
        ],
        'leadtime_hour': ['0'],
        'area': [
            40.9, 23.4, 40.2, 24.1, #bbox for Ihalainen 61.4, 27.5, 60.6, 28.9,
        ],
        'format': 'netcdf_zip'
    }
)
```

MODIS

```
earthaccess.login()
# Search for Terra data (MOD04_3K)
terra_files = earthaccess.search_data(
    short_name='MOD04_3K',
    bounding_box=bounding_box,
    temporal=(start_date, end_date)
)

# Search for Aqua data (MYD04_L2)
aqua_files = earthaccess.search_data(
    short_name='MYD04_3K',
    bounding_box=bounding_box,
    temporal=(start_date, end_date)
)

# Combine Terra and Aqua file results
all_files = terra_files + aqua_files
aod_data = hdf_file.select('Optical_Depth_Land_And_Ocean')[:] # Optical_Depth_Land_And_Ocean
```

Appendix 2.

Additional settings for prediction models Prophet, BSTS, Random Forest and XGBoost in R programming language.

BSTS

```
library(bsts)

# select column
cams_MAM25_26 <- ch_cams_t_cl_monthly$cams_mam_25_26_m
dates <- ch_cams_t_cl_monthly$Month_Start

# train, test and future datasets split
train_data <- cams_MAM25_26[dates <= as.Date("2023-12-31")]
test_data <- cams_MAM25_26[dates > as.Date("2023-12-31") & dates <= as.Date("2024-08-31")]
future_dates <- seq(from = as.Date("2024-09-01"), to = as.Date("2025-12-31"), by = "month")

# definition of BSTS components
state_spec <- list()
state_spec <- AddSemilocalLinearTrend(state_spec, train_data) # semilocal trend
state_spec <- AddSeasonal(state_spec, train_data, nseasons = 12) # monthly seasonality

# model fit
bsts_model <- bsts(train_data, state.specification = state_spec, niter = 1000)

# predictions
forecast_horizon <- length(test_data) + length(future_dates)
predictions <- predict(bsts_model, horizon = forecast_horizon)

# extracting predictions for visualization
test_predictions <- predictions$mean[1:length(test_data)]
future_predictions <- predictions$mean[(length(test_data) + 1):forecast_horizon]

test_dates <- dates[dates > as.Date("2023-12-31") & dates <= as.Date("2024-08-31")]
results <- data.frame(
  Date = c(test_dates, future_dates),
  Prediction = c(test_predictions, future_predictions)
)

# validation metrics
correlation <- cor(test_data, test_predictions, method = "spearman")
RMSE <- sqrt(mean((test_data - test_predictions)^2))
mae <- mean(abs(test_data - test_predictions))
```

PROPHET

```
library(prophet)

train_data <- ch_cams_t_cl_monthly %>% filter(Month_Start < "2024-01-02")
test_data <- ch_cams_t_cl_monthly %>% filter(Month_Start > "2023-12-31")

# data preparation
prophet_data <- train_data %>%
  select(Month_Start, cams_mam_25_26_m) %>%
  rename(ds = Month_Start, y = cams_mam_25_26_m)

# model fitting
m <- prophet()
m <- fit.prophet(m, prophet_data)

# future time dataframe
future <- make_future_dataframe(m, periods = 24, freq = "month")

# prediction
forecast <- predict(m, future)
# data combination for visualization
forecast <- forecast %>%
  select(ds, yhat, yhat_lower, yhat_upper)

combined_data <- full_join(
  test_data %>% rename(ds = Month_Start, y_true = cams_mam_25_26_m),
  forecast,
  by = "ds"
)
# correlations and validation metrics
valid_data <- combined_data %>%
  filter(!is.na(y_true) & !is.na(yhat))
correlation <- cor(valid_data$y_true, valid_data$yhat, method = "spearman")
rmse <- sqrt(mean((valid_data$y_true - valid_data$yhat)^2))
mae <- mean(abs(valid_data$y_true - valid_data$yhat))
prophet_data$ds <- as.POSIXct(prophet_data$ds)
```

RANDOM FOREST

```
library(randomForest)
library(caret)

# set training schema
train_control <- trainControl(method = "cv", number = 5)

# set values range for parameters
tune_grid <- expand.grid( mtry = c(2, 4, 6, 8) )

# train model with cross validation
rf_model <- train(
  y ~ ., data = train_data,
  method = "rf",
  trControl = train_control,
  tuneGrid = tune_grid,
  ntree = 500,
  importance = TRUE,
```

```

    nodesize = 10,
    na.action = na.roughfix
  )
  best_rf_model <- rf_model$finalModel

# predictions
predictions <- predict(best_rf_model, newdata = test_data)

# validation metrics
results_rf <- data.frame(date = dates, actual = test_data$y, predicted_rf = predictions)
rmse <- sqrt(mean((results_rf$actual - results_rf$predicted)^2))
print(paste("Optimized RMSE:", rmse))
r <- cor(results_rf$actual, results_rf$predicted)
print(paste("R:", r))
print(best_rf_model)

```

XGBOOST

```

library(xgboost)
library(lubridate)

# data selection
data <- ch_cams_t_cl %>% filter(!is.na(cams_mam_21_24)) %>% select(Date, cams_mam_21_24)
data <- ch_cams_t_cl %>%
  filter(!is.na(cams_mam_21_24)) %>%
  select(Date, cams_mam_21_24) %>%
  mutate(month = month(Date))

# make as time series
ts_data <- ts(data$cams_mam_21_24, start = c(2015, 01, 01), frequency = 365.25)

# lag function
create_lags <- function(ts, k) {
  lagged_data <- embed(ts, k + 1)
  colnames(lagged_data) <- c("y", paste0("lag_", 1:k))
  return(as.data.frame(lagged_data))
}

# set lag values
lags <- 8
data_with_lags <- create_lags(ts_data, lags)
data_with_lags$month <- data$month[(lags + 1):nrow(data)]

# train and test data split
train_size <- ch_all_datasets %>%
  filter(Date < '2024-01-01') %>%
  nrow() %>%
  -lags
train_data <- data_with_lags[1:train_size, ]
test_data <- data_with_lags[(train_size + 1):nrow(data_with_lags), ]
dates <- ch_all_datasets %>%
  filter(Date > '2024-01-01' & Date < '2024-09-01') %>%
  pull(Date)

# data prep
dtrain <- xgb.DMatrix(data = as.matrix(train_data[, -1]), label = train_data$y, missing = NaN)

```

```

dtest <- xgb.DMatrix(data = as.matrix(test_data[, -1]), label = test_data$y, missing = NaN)

# parameters setting
params <- list(
  booster = "gbtree",
  objective = "reg:squarederror",
  max_depth = 5,
  eta = 0.1,
  subsample = 0.7,
  colsample_bytree = 0.8
)

# train model with cross validation and early stopping
cv <- xgb.cv(
  params = params,
  data = dtrain,
  nrounds = 800,
  nfold = 5,
  early_stopping_rounds = 20,
  maximize = FALSE,
  print_every_n = 10
)
best_nrounds <- cv$best_iteration

# final model training
xgb_model <- xgb.train(params, dtrain, nrounds = best_nrounds)

# predictions
predictions <- predict(xgb_model, newdata = dtest)

# results comparision
results_xg <- data.frame(date = dates, actual = test_data$y, predicted_xg = predictions)
rmse <- sqrt(mean((results_xg$actual - results_xg$predicted_xg)^2))
print(paste("RMSE:", rmse))
r <- cor(results_xg$actual, results_xg$predicted_xg)
print(paste("R:", r))

```